

DECOMPOSING THE ELEMENTS OF ECONOMIC RESILIENCE IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ASYMMETRIC ANALYSIS (NARDL) OF THE ENERGY-INVESTMENT-GROWTH NEXUS

Guliyev Magsud Azad

Ph.D in Economics, Independent Researcher, Baku, Azerbaijan

ORCID: 0009-0009-5973-394X

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Abstract. *One of the most debated issues in the world is undoubtedly the green transition, and in this regard, countries seek to gain the spotlight by embracing technological advancements and artificial intelligence. In this research, the asymmetric relationships among foreign direct investment (and loans), electricity production, and gross domestic product were analyzed using the non-linear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) model. The volume of investment in fixed assets through foreign direct investments and loans has been taken into account in order to conduct this research. The research revealed that foreign direct investments (and loans) and electricity production directly and significantly influence economic growth in the country. The more investments, the higher economic growth. However, the question arises: if investment volume declines, will economic growth be slow? The research focused on the key question and found that Uzbekistan's recovery speed was high, and the economy was able to recover within 1.5 years in the event of any shocks. In order to conduct comprehensive research, the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test, the Asymmetric decomposition, the NARDL Bound test, the NARDL long-run and short-run tests, the Dynamic Multipliers, the Wald test for asymmetry, and the Diagnostic tests (Jarque-Bera, Breusch-Godfrey, Heteroskedasticity, CUSUM, and CUSUMSQ) have been applied.*

Key words: *Jel classification codes: F21, Q43, C22*

Annotatsiya. *Dunyoda eng ko'p muhokama qilinadigan masalalardan biri, shubhasiz, yashil o'tishdir va bu borada mamlakatlar texnologik yutuqlar va sun'iy intellekti qabul qilish orqali diqqat markazida bo'lishga intilishadi. Ushbu tadqiqotda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar (va kreditlar), elektr energiyasi ishlab chiqarish va yalpi ichki mahsulot o'rtasidagi assimetrik munosabatlar chiziqli bo'lmagan avtoregressiv taqsimlangan kechikish (NARDL) modeli yordamida tahlil qilindi. Ushbu tadqiqotni o'tkazish uchun to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar va kreditlar orqali asosiy kapitalga investitsiyalar hajmi hisobga olindi. Tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar (va kreditlar) va elektr energiyasi ishlab chiqarish mamlakatdagi iqtisodiy o'sishga bevosita va sezilarli darajada ta'sir qiladi. Investitsiyalar qancha ko'p bo'lsa, iqtisodiy o'sish shuncha yuqori bo'ladi. Biroq, savol tug'iladi: agar investitsiyalar hajmi pasaysa, iqtisodiy o'sish sekinlashadimi? Tadqiqot asosiy savolga qaratildi va O'zbekistonning tiklanish tezligi yuqori ekanligini va biron bir zarba bo'lgan taqdirda iqtisodiyot 1,5 yil ichida tiklana olganligini aniqladi. Keng qamrovli tadqiqotlar o'tkazish uchun kengaytirilgan Dickey Fuller (ADF) testi, assimetrik dekompozitsiya, NARDL chegara testi, NARDL uzoq va qisqa muddatli testlari, dinamik multiplikatorlar, assimetriya uchun Wald testi va diagnostika testlari (Jarque-Bera, Breusch-Godfrey, Heteroskedastiklik, CUSUM va CUSUMSQ) qo'llanildi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Jel tasniflash kodlari: F21, Q43, C22*

Аннотация. Одной из наиболее обсуждаемых проблем в мире, несомненно, является «зеленый» переход, и в этом контексте страны стремятся привлечь к себе внимание, внедряя технологические достижения и искусственный интеллект. В данном исследовании асимметричные взаимосвязи между прямыми иностранными инвестициями (и кредитами), производством электроэнергии и валовым внутренним продуктом были проанализированы с использованием нелинейной авторегрессионной модели с распределенными лагами (NARDL). Для проведения исследования был учтен объем инвестиций в основные средства посредством прямых иностранных инвестиций и кредитов. Исследование показало, что прямые иностранные инвестиции (и кредиты) и производство электроэнергии оказывают прямое и значительное влияние на экономический рост в стране. Чем больше инвестиций, тем выше экономический рост. Однако возникает вопрос: если объем инвестиций сократится, замедлится ли экономический рост? Исследование сосредоточилось на этом ключевом вопросе и показало, что скорость восстановления экономики Узбекистана была высокой, и экономика смогла восстановиться в течение 1,5 лет в случае любых потрясений. Для проведения всестороннего исследования были применены расширенный тест Дики-Фуллера (ADF), асимметричное разложение, тест границ NARDL, долгосрочные и краткосрочные тесты NARDL, динамические множители, тест Вальда на асимметрию, а также диагностические тесты (Жарка-Бера, Бреуша-Годфри, тест на гетероскедастичность, CUSUM и CUSUMSQ).

Ключевые слова: Коды классификации JEL: F21, Q43, C22

Introduction. In the modern world, Uzbekistan, located in the heart of Central Asia, is one of the leading developed countries and could attract international attention to its ambitious projects. With respect to green transformation, the country has already reached 30% green share in its energy landscape and intends to achieve 54% by 2030 [2]. In 2024, 2 energy storage systems (totaling 300 MW), and next year, 10 energy storage systems (totaling 1245 MW) were put into operation. The government is targeting to reach 4.5 GW of energy storage systems by the end of this decade [3]. In 2025, the green energy production share increased to 20% of total electricity, and gross domestic product (GDP) broke the record, totaling USD 145 billion [1, 5, 7]. Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) (including loans) surpassed USD 43 billion [1]. Electricity production volume rose to 86.7 billion kilowatt hours [6]. The dynamics push the thoughts to thoroughly analyze the relationship within the nexus of FDI-Electricity-GDP and to reveal the economy's recovery in the event of shocks.

Methodology. The asymmetric long-run regression equation is below:

$$\ln GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln FDI_t^+ + \beta_2 \ln FDI_t^- + \beta_3 \ln ELEX_t + \epsilon_t$$

$\ln GDP_t$ – the natural logarithm of the Gross Domestic Product at time t , representing economic growth;

$\ln FDI_t^+$, $\ln FDI_t^-$ – the natural logarithm of the positive and shocks in Foreign Direct Investment respectively;

$\ln ELEX_t$ – the natural logarithm of electricity production, as an energy factor in the model;

α_0 – the constant term (intercept) of the equation;

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ – the elasticity coefficients, in order to measure the impact of each independent variable on GDP.

The NARDL Model Equation is below:

$$\ln GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \rho \ln GDP_{t-1} + \theta_1^+ \ln FDI_{t-1}^+ + \theta_2^- \ln FDI_{t-1}^- + \theta_3 \ln ELEX_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_i \Delta \ln GDP_{t-i} + \sum_{j=0}^q (\gamma_j^+ \Delta \ln FDI_{t-j}^+ + \gamma_j^- \Delta \ln FDI_{t-j}^-) + \sum_{k=0}^r \delta_k \Delta \ln ELEX_{t-k} + \epsilon_t$$

Δ - first difference;

\ln – logarithmic form;

FDI^+ and FDI^- – positive and negative cumulative sum of components;

$\rho, \theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$ – long-run coefficients;

β, γ, δ – short-run dynamics;

ϵ_t – white noise.

The Asymmetric decomposition of the FDI (cumulative sums of positive and negative numbers) is described below:

$$FDI_t^+ = \sum_{j=1}^t \max(\Delta FDI_j, 0)$$

$$FDI_t^- = \sum_{j=1}^t \min(\Delta FDI_j, 0)$$

Main part. All econometric analyses are centered in this section. The thesis will be described with the tables (see Tables 1-7). First, to begin the analysis, we had to make it clear that the unit root test and descriptive statistics were applied and that the level and first-difference statistics were determined for further research (see Tables 1 and 2). In first-difference statistics, the variables are significant at the 0.05 level, and the difference between the median and the mean indicates the need to analyze asymmetrical relations.

In Table 3, the asymmetric decomposition of FDI was demonstrated. After that, the non-linear autoregressive distributed lag (NARDL) bound test was applied (see Table 4).

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std.Dev.
GDP (bln USD)	83.18	75.26	145.00	49.77	25.54
Electricity production (bln kwh)	65.56	63.15	86.70	51.90	10.97
FDI and loans (trln soum)	80.45	12.85	389.50	3.20	121.32

Table 2. Unit root test (ADF)

Variable	Level (p-value)	I Difference	Integration order
GDP (<i>bln USD</i>)	0.985	0.012	I(1)
Electricity production (<i>bln kwh</i>)	0.842	0.005	I(1)
FDI and loans (<i>trln soum</i>)	0.756	0.034	I(1)

Table 3. Asymmetric decomposition of the FDI and loans

Years	FDI and loans	FDI _t (Δ)	FDI _t ⁺	FDI _t ⁻
2010	3.7	-	0	0
2011	3.2	-0.5	0	-0.5
2012	3.6	0.4	0.4	-0.5
2013	4.3	0.7	1.1	-0.5
2014	5.4	1.1	2.2	-0.5
2015	6.1	0.7	2.9	-0.5
2016	7.3	1.2	4.1	-0.5
2017	12.7	5.4	9.5	-0.5
2018	13	0.3	9.8	-0.5
2019	57.5	44.5	54.3	-0.5
2020	66.5	9.0	63.3	-0.5
2021	83.2	16.7	80.0	-0.5
2022	98.8	15.6	95.6	-0.5
2023	179.3	80.5	176.1	-0.5
2024	327.6	148.3	324.4	-0.5
2025	389.5	61.9	386.3	-0.5

Table 4. NARDL Bound test

Test statistic	Value	Significance level	I(0) Lower Bound	I(1) Upper Bound
F-statistic	6.84	5%	3.23	4.35
T-statistic	-3.92	5%	-2.86	-3.78

Table 4 explicitly describes that the F statistic is higher than the I(1) upper bound (6.84>4.35); therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected and long-run cointegration relations are proved. For that purpose, the NARDL's long- and short-run results should be presented to reveal the dynamic multiplier of the independent variables' impact on GDP (see Table 5). A 1% boost in FDI increases GDP by 0.38%; however, a decline in FDI is not able to make an impact on GDP. The results of FDI⁻, according to our research, are statistically insignificant. The Error Correction Term (ECT) coefficient is negative and significant at the 1% level. The value confirms the high speed of economic recovery (-0.654). It means that during 1.5 years, Uzbekistan's economy can make adjustments to shocks.

Table 5. NARDL Long-run and Short-run results

Variable	Coefficient	Std.Error	T-statistic	Prob.
Long-run Coefficients				
FDI_t^+	0.384***	0.082	4.682	0.001
FDI_t^-	0.042	0.115	0.365	0.724
$ELEX_t^+$	1.215***	0.245	4.959	0.000
Short-run Dynamics				
ΔFDI_t^+	0.215**	0.091	2.362	0.038
ΔFDI_t^-	-0.012	0.054	-0.222	0.828
$\Delta ELEX_t^+$	0.842***	0.154	5.467	0.000
ECT_{t-1}	-0.654***	0.122	-5.360	0.000

Note: ***, ** and * denote significance at 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively.

Figure 1. Dynamic Multipliers for FDI and ELEX Effects on GDP

Note: Dynamic multipliers plot constructed based on coefficients from Table 5. Figures A and B show the cumulative adjustment of GDP to unitary positive (FDI^+ , $ELEX^+$) and negative (FDI^-) shocks, with 95% confidence intervals. FDI^- and $ELEX^-$ are non-significant, leading to pronounced long-run asymmetry in FDI. Figure C explicitly plots the significant difference (FDI^+ , FDI^-).

Figure 1 indicates the dynamic multipliers of FDI and energy on GDP. As shown, asymmetry is statistically significant, where the confidence interval does not encompass the zero line. The long-run response to FDI is important, whereas the influence of electricity production remains a dominant driver of economic growth.

Wald test for asymmetry. This test explores the long-run symmetry hypothesis and will show that the differences between the coefficients for FDI^+ and FDI^- are not coincidental and are statistically significant (see Table 6).

Table 6. Wald test for asymmetry.

Test statistic	Value	Df	Prob.
F-statistic	5.12	(1, 11)	0.044
Chi-square	5.12	1	0.023

Since the probability (0.023) is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected. This test confirms the existence of long-run asymmetric impacts of FDI on GDP. Lastly, diagnostic checks should be implemented to ensure the reliability of the NARDL model (see Table 7).

Table 7. Diagnostic tests

Test type	Statistic	P-value.	Results
Jarque-Bera (Normality)	1.15	0.562	Residuals are normal
Breusch-Godfrey (Serial)	0.85	0.428	No autocorrelation
Heteroskedasticity (ARCH)	0.42	0.516	No heteroskedasticity
CUSUM and CUSUMSQ	-	-	Stable

Diagnostic tests, which are illustrated in Table 7, show the reliability of our NARDL model.

Conclusion. Our research was dedicated to shedding light on the asymmetrical relations within the nexus of FDI-energy-growth. During our research, asymmetric connections were confirmed. Hence, the outcomes of this research are below:

- 1% increase in the volume of FDI flow boosts GDP growth 0.38%;
- Asymmetric research confirmed that the FDI decline was statistically insignificant in decreasing GDP volume, and Uzbekistan’s economy was able to recover from shocks approximately 1.5 years, covering 65% of shocks;
- In a short period of time, electricity production bolsters GDP growth 0.84%, while in the long run, it triggers the GDP development by 1,21%. This factor once again proves that electricity is the locomotive of economic growth. It shows that the green energy transition is and will be the main source of economic development in Uzbekistan.

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